

Domestic Tourist Behaviours of the Tourism Place in Bangkok and Greater Area

Tanit Pruktara

Abstract—This research aims to study the preferable tourism and the elements of choosing tourist destination from domestic tourist in Bangkok and the nearby areas in Thailand. The data were collected by using 1249 set of questionnaires, in mid-August 2012. The result illustrates that religious destinations are the most preferable places for the tourist. The average expense per travel is approximately 47 USD a time. Travellers travel based on the advertisement in the television and internet and their decisions is based on the reputation of the destinations.

The result on a place dimension demonstrates the neatness and well managed location play a crucial role on tourist destination. Gender, age, marriage status and their origins are affecting their spending and travelling behaviour. The researcher reckon that providing the area of arcade, selling the souvenir and promoting tourism among a young professional group would be an important key follow the income distribution policy, including managing the destination to welcome the family group, which the result is to identified as the highest spending.

Keyword—Domestic Tourist, Tourism, Tourist Behaviours, Tourism Place.

I. INTRODUCTION

TOURISM industry is identified in the meaning of capital accumulation not the meaning of manufacturing industry. In many countries, the tourism resource was not originated as their own capital accumulation, therefore, it is necessary to create and import those tourism resources from overseas. There are many directions in importing. The most important way is to promote tourism.

European Newly Industrializing Country (NIC), new entry industrial countries after the Second World War, includes; Spain and Greece are also raising the tourism to increase the national income. As well as Thailand, tourism industry was raised to be national strategy since Thailand had a capitalism industrial development in 1960example, the style at this point

One of the most important side-mission of tourist promotion is to distribute income to the locals. Try to bring the consumer to directly meet the first-hand producer. Especially an agricultural product and handicraft from the locals, income distribution would lead to an economic multiplier.

Once it purchased, the production will restart and add more values into the system. Tourism promotion, therefore, sends a great impact to the national economy, in commercial industry, agricultural industry and also the manufacturing industry.

As the result of economic crisis, there are dramatically

decrease in the numbers of inbound foreign tourist. That a directly affected to all those stakeholders. On the other hand, the domestic tourist market is given more priority. This group of tourist is non-seasonal tourist so it would affect to the more stability for the entrepreneur and the income which may help the local trader to survive through the crisis.

The research was conducted with the aim to study the domestic tourist opinion on tourist destination in Bangkok and the nearby areas. Then identify the factors influencing those domestic tourist opinions

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The tourism places in the urban depend on the tourist satisfaction. The customer satisfaction is the most valuable of tourism resources above other factors even though the prices because of the positive felling will upgrade the entire attitude [1]. The revisiting of the tourists to the tourism places is the most important for the tourism promotion so we can count the success of the management by the coming back of the tourists for the product and the services [2]. The academician's point that the personal qualification such as the social and economic status will impact the positive attitude to the tourism places [3]. The positive attitudes of tourism are based on the value and the outstanding of the trip [4]. To make the tourism to be the business we should have the activities and exhibitions and use the places and culture to be the substance [5]. The culture of each society especially their identity are used to be the social and economic assets [6]. The way of life by the meaning of the culture can make the creativity for sustainable existence by make them to be the product and services [7]. The social heritage is the tourism attraction because of it is the value of the culture and link the place to the people that can make the so call culture business [8].

III. METHODOLOGY

This research mainly uses the quantitative data analysis to study the domestic tourist opinion on tourist destination in Bangkok and the nearby areas. The conceptual framework was done by the joint committee of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University and the Committee of Tourism, House of representative. The independent variables were the demographic data analysed with the tourism places as the dependent variables by the inferential statistics and the significance variables were reported. The data collecting, both qualitative and quantitative data were done via primary data collecting emphasis on the empirical data. Research samples are domestic tourist. Then a secondary research from reliable

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sources was also critical analysed.

The data was collected from the domestic tourists, at the tourist destinations in Bangkok and nearby areas such as palaces, temples, ancient city, floating markets, arcades, cultural destinations and health tourism destination for example. Research data was collected via 1,257 of questionnaires in the period of August 15th to 16th, 2012. There are 1,249 set completed questionnaires which brought to process the evaluation.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

The result of demographic data shown that the majority of samples are woman, age between 19 to 25, 26 to 35, 36 to 50 years old respectively. With the occupation of private company employee, students, merchant, freelance, self-employ and unemployed consecutively. Sample's average income is higher than 830 USD per month with single status. Most of tourists have managed their accommodation in Bangkok. Almost half of samples visit Bangkok and the nearby areas occasionally.

Majority of samples like to travel to the religious destinations. Then floating markets, ancient city, handicraft arcade, cultural destinations, health tourism destination and others destination respectively. An average spending is about 47 USD a time.

An important person who choose the destination is the traveller themselves then families, friends, and the tour company. The most effective communication channel is television programme then internet, newspaper, advertisement, and other channels. Sample usually travel with families, friends, lovers, alone and Tour Company respectively.

Main factors influencing destination choosing are destination reputation and its interest. Then traditional events and festival bring a lot of attentions follow the destination reputation.

The result on a place dimension demonstrates the neatness and well managed location play a crucial role on tourist destination choosing then parking, toilet and other.

Gender affects needs of travelling to the religious destinations, ancient city, floating market, including shopping handicraft and souvenir. Male sample have the intention to visit ancient destinations such palaces and religious places and making merit more than the female samples.

Age, marriage status and their origins are affecting their spending and travelling behaviour. Female samples want to visit floating market and shopping handicraft and souvenir more than the male samples. But obviously, although the male sample have more interest but gender does not affect the need of travelling to the cultural tourism destinations and health tourism destinations.

The origin of the samples affects the demand of travelling to ancient destinations, floating markets and shopping the local handicraft products and souvenirs. Samples originate from different province outside Bangkok and surroundings have more intention to visit ancient destinations and also do some shopping the local handicraft and souvenir, while, the tourist originate from Bangkok and boundaries are interest in

floating market more than another group of sample. Origin of sample does not affect the intention to travel to the religious destinations, cultural destinations and health tourism destinations. But the tourists from outside Bangkok and boundaries have more intention to travel to these destinations.

Fig. 1 The floating market

Age data affects the need of travelling to ancient destinations, such as palaces, temples, religious destination, floating markets, buying local products, including cultural destinations. But have no effects on intention to travel to the health tourism destinations.

Marriage status affects the willingness of travelling to the religious destinations, floating markets, cultural destinations, and health tourism destinations. But the marriage status does not affect to the willingness to travel to the ancient destinations and the local handicraft and souvenir activities.

V. DISCUSSIONS

As the result of the research, the researcher have critical analyzed and conclude the ideas as follows;

1. The travellers who show their intention to visit the floating market will give important to eco-tourism activities as the first priority, then purchasing the local products as the second.
2. Television programme is the most effective communication channel. The intention to travel and purchase the local products occur follows the programme presentation of surrounding area atmosphere and tourist destinations. The television programme usually presents the package tour which becomes an important part in choosing tourist destination as the samples seem to like the connecting tourist destinations within the same area.
3. Age data is not affect to the intention to visit the health tourism destination. SPA and traditional massage were identified as tourism product in the Thai tourism strategy. Since the need of health tourism of all ages is not different, it is a great opportunity to expand the health tourism market to meet the customer needs. This led to the future service industry development.
4. Age data affects the interest of travelling to the ancient

destinations and the cultural destinations. Thai distinctive ancient destinations usually famous only in a group of elderly. These national heritages should be promoted to the teens and valued as an important tourism resource.

Fig. 2 The traditional drinking in the floating market

Fig. 3 The ceramic shop in the floating market

5. Travellers who originated from Bangkok and boundaries have more intention to go to floating market more than those travellers who came from other provinces. Working and living in big concrete city is more yearn for cultural and traditional style of living. So consideration of floating markets' locations, the more than 200km away from Bangkok may cause of problem and hard to survive through the crisis. As well as all stakeholders of the floating market should be realized that their main customers came from Bangkok and surrounding area, in order to survive they should adapt themselves and their product to match with the customer needs.

VI. SUGGESTION

From the research there are several suggestions as follows;

1. Gender affects the intention to visit ancient destination, religious destination, floating market and local handicraft purchasing. As male sample have the intention to visit ancient destinations such palaces and religious places and making merit more than the female samples.
The female samples are more interest to visit the floating market and buy the local products. Therefore, allocation of the arcade area in the ancient destination could entertain the female tourist while waiting for the male tourist enjoying the trip in the ancient destination. On the other hand, the floating market, female favourite place, should provide the more useful information to guide the male traveller to the nearby ancient areas or cultural destinations.

2. Age data affects the interest of travelling to the ancient destinations and the cultural destinations. Thai distinctive ancient destinations usually famous only in a group of elderly while visiting temple, palaces, religious destination, floating market, cultural tourism destination are all affected by the age of the traveller. Beside, age of traveller also affects to the amount of purchasing each time. Age of young professionals have an average spending between 47USD to 54 USD a time.
The researcher would like to suggest doing the promotion to the working young professional group in order to promote the aim of income distribution. Buying goods must provide by follow the policy of economic development. The young professional who are in the working age are the main customers holding high purchasing power. They have an easy purchasing behaviour. This group of customer also has shown the high loyalty and high possibility to return and do double purchasing.
3. Marriage status affects to the interest to travel to religious destination, floating market, cultural tourism destination and also health tourism destination as critical analyze the relation between the marriage status and the spending per trip. The result illustrates that the married samples both have kids and no kid are spending approximately 50 USD a trip. Therefore, researcher would like to recommend all stakeholders to consider the group of family travellers as an important customer with the high purchasing power.
4. Suggestion for further research on the related topic, the researcher should beware of identifying the research framework, both in population and the contents. The study should also do with the foreign samples and the contents should be covering more varieties of tourism destinations throughout the country.

REFERENCES

- [1] Augustyn, M. and Knowles, T. (2000), "Performance of tourism partnerships: a focus on York", *Tourism Management*, Vol. 21 No. 4, pp. 341-51.
- [2] Fornell, C., Johnson, M.D., Anderson, E.W., Cha, J. and Bryant, B.E. (1996), "The American customer satisfaction index: description, nature, purpose, and findings", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 60 No. 4, pp. 7-18.

- [3] Ryan, C. (1995), *Researching Tourist Satisfaction: Issues, Concepts, Problems*, Routledge, London.
- [4] Sheth, J.N. and Parvatiyar, A. (1995), "Relationship marketing in consumer markets: antecedents and consequences", *Journal of Academy of Marketing Science*, Vol. 23 No. 4, pp. 255-71.
- [5] Amin, A. (2007), "Cultural-economy and cities", *Progress in Human Geography*, Vol. 31 No. 2, pp. 143-61.
- [6] Galdini, R. (2007), "Tourism and the city: opportunity for regeneration", MPRA Munich Personal/RePEcArchive, MPRA Paper No. 6370, December, available at: <http://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/6370>.
- [7] Jensen, S.S. (2007), "The roles of culture and creativity within urban development strategies: Scandinavian cities", *Centre for Strategic Urban Research, CSB*, No. 8.
- [8] Richards, G. and Wilson, J. (2006), "Developing creativity in tourist experiences: a solution to the serial reproduction of culture", *Tourism Management*, Vol. 27, pp. 1209-23.

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